

Treatment Plan Generations

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Abstract- The Introduction of Machine Learning (ML) has significantly revolutionized health care in its various fields. The data that is generated exponentially at each second in health platforms across hospitals or health related platforms significantly contributes to the doctor recommendations, disease prediction, generation of the precautions related to the disease . Traditionally, visiting the doctors may be the only way to receive the doctor treatment and medicine suggestions related to the disease. But the Machine Learning approach lets us analyse all generated historical data of the patients from doctor consultations and trusted sources to produce recommendations of precautions related to each disease and medical conditions. Efficient doctor suggestions can be generated based on the doctor consultation history's based on the patient's current health status or disease. The intention of the system is to generate a treatment plan that comprises best doctor suggestions, precautions related to and suggest medicines with doctor recommendation warning.

Keywords- Machine Learning (ML), Healthcare Revolution), Doctor Recommendation, Precaution Generation, Historical Medical Data, Treatment Plan Generation, Doctor Consultation History, Personalized Healthcare, Medicine Suggestion, AI-driven Healthcare Solutions

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital data collection of the medical history of patients has significantly improved the development of efficient ml models that can assist in doctor recommendations, medicine recommendations and precautions generation. Traditionally, visiting doctors was the only way to identify the disease based on the symptoms. But recent technical advancements and the availability of efficient Machine Learning Algorithms lead to creating efficient models on reliable and authentic data available across health platforms . As the health data is sensitive , the handling of the medical data would be more secure and wouldn't be shared with any unauthorized users. The usage of the model and the data would be strictly for the intended purpose which would be suggestions of the best doctors based on the locality, disease and medical

suggestions would be related to the disease and the current health condition of the patient.

The precautions would be generated using the Gemini API which would be giving almost reliable results and could also generate reliable precautions based on the current and previous medical history. The precautions include exercises, food related suggestions. The primary objectives of this research are:

- To develop and implement a predictive system that assists in personalized treatment planning.
- To provide best doctor recommendations based on a patient's data such as location, disease etc.
- To generate precautionary measures that help patients take proactive steps in managing their conditions.
- To provide suggestive doctor recommendations based on a patient's data or disease name which includes the information whether medicine prescription needed or not
- To improve the accuracy and accessibility of healthcare through AI-driven medical advice

The goal of the study to enhance the effectiveness of the healthcare by streamlining the health related information that could be accessed and known from the comfort of not visiting the hospital or doctor personally

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, there have been very notable changes in healthcare with the introduction of AI. Data driven approaches have significantly improved patient outcomes and also patients medical experiences. The inclusion of Artificial Intelligence in health care could

facilitate enhanced medical decision-making and can bring remarkable changes in the domain of personalized medicine.

The role of Artificial intelligence driven approaches in the medical field has been explored recently. Fröhlich et al. [3] emphasized that data science can play a significant role in providing personalized treatment by relying on patient oriented data such as genetic profiles for clinical decision making. It states the potential of Artificial Intelligence in identifying therapeutic interventions by considering each individual's medical history. Similarly, Schork [5] examined the convergence of AI and personalised medicine, showing how machine learning models can predict treatment responses and suggest therapies based on specific patient needs.

The significance of Artificial Intelligence has also been explored and analyzed further broadly in healthcare applications. Javaid et al. [4] has categorized the Artificial Intelligence applications in healthcare into different sections such as predictive analytics, clinical decision support and patient monitoring. The research has noted how much AI-driven automation has helped in reducing human error and optimizing healthcare delivery. Bruckert et al. [4] proposed how AI driven diagnostics enhances clinical trust and interpretability of machine generated recommendations.

The Artificial Intelligence applications in precision healthcare has also been explored in the context of mathematical modelling and contextual data analysis. Colijn et al. [2] has analysed the challenges faced and the opportunities created in precision healthcare and emphasized the use of mathematical frameworks in modeling complex biological systems for accurate disease prediction. The research also highlighted the integration of AI with domain specific knowledge would improve the reliability and healthcare model applicability.

Overall, these studies summarized the potential of AI in transforming personalized medicine suggestions and healthcare decision making efficiently. The inclusion of Artificial Intelligence proved bringing significant benefits in terms of accuracy in prediction, patient centered care, and decision support for medical professionals. However, challenges related to areas like transparency, ethical considerations, and the interpretability of AI models remain and have to be researched in future. Our work builds a treatment plan that can include suggested best doctors , suggested

medicines and precautions based on the patient data or particular disease.

III.SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The system implementation presents a detailed framework for a healthcare assistant that predicts the best doctor and suggests precautions based on medical conditions. This system integrates machine learning for doctor recommendations, medication predictions, and generating precautions. The implementation is structured around a Flask based backend and a React-based frontend.

A. System Architecture of the Service

The system follows an architecture with 3 primary components in a modular way:

- Doctor prediction and recommendation module
- Medicine prediction module
- Patient education and precaution suggestion module

These components are include in a healthcare platform with the frontend in react and the Machine Learning Service implement using flask which is served through created api that triggers the function serving the doctor recommendations and medicine recommendation where the input values are the disease name and the patients health related details passed as JSON .The user details are present in mongodb

B. Doctor Prediction and Recommendation

The System predicts the most suitable doctors for a given disease or medical condition.

- Model Training

The Model is trained using Random Forest Classifier with the categorical values encoded using label encoder into numerical values. The trained model is saved using pickle

- Prediction Workflow

The ML model is run on the server and serviced outside through flask api. Frontend is created using the react and the values for the prediction is sent to the Predictor as JSON and the result is sent back as JSON and the frontend calls the backend which is implement with express node js to retrieve doctor details that are

suggested from the doctor details present in the MongoDB

C. Doctor Prediction and Recommendation

The System predicts the best Medicines for a given disease or medical condition.

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The Model is trained using Random Forest Classifier with the categorical values encoded using label encoder into numerical values. The trained model is saved using pickle

- Prediction Workflow

The ML model is run on the server and serviced outside through flask api. Frontend is created using the react and the values for the prediction is sent to the Predictor as JSON and the result is sent back as JSON and the frontend calls the backend which is implement with express node js to retrieve Medicine details that are suggested from the Medicine details present in the MongoDB

D. Precaution Suggestion

Google's Gemini Api service is used to deliver the precautions to the input disease or medical condition.

Once the user inputs the disease name, the Gemini API creates the suggested precautions to the disease and the result is presented in a neat format using React Markdown

E. API Integration

The system provide the apis created for accessing the ml service developed for serving

doctor recommendations: '/predict' triggers the ml doctor predictor service that services the suggested doctors

Medicine recommendations: '/med_predict' triggers the ml medicine predictor service that services the suggested medicine

Precaution suggestion : '/precaution' calls the gemini api to create structure precautions for a medicines as a suggestion

IV. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

The system was evaluated across multiple dimensions to assess its performance and effectiveness in enhancing prediction results.

Figure 1-Performance Metrics

A. Comparative Analysis

- Doctor prediction accuracy: 88.96%
- Medicine recommendation accuracy: 85.75%
- API response time: Within 500ms
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B. Performance

The system processes the input data passed as JSON and responds to the result much faster. The data fetching of the doctors, medicine from the mongodb and the response from the gemini api of the suggested precautions is much faster.

These results validate the system's capability of predicting the results such as doctor recommendations, medicine recommendations and generating precautions much faster and efficiently.

V. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of the research could be identified in the below areas :

A. Advanced Model Optimization

Improved predictions and accuracy of the classifications can be achieved by concentrating on:

- Implementation of the deep learning techniques for accuracy of the classification.
- Reducing model complexity to optimize performance on low-resource devices.
- Leveraging federated learning for privacy-preserving model training.

B. Expanded Data Sources

To improve the efficiency and accuracy of predictions :

- Realtime data streams from IoT and partner APIs in a consistent fashion. Social media sentiment analysis (unstructured)
- Improving domain knowledge based feature engineering
- Making use of domain specific feature engineering as well.

C. Real-time Prediction and Automation

Currently, predictions are generated on demand. Implementing real time processing enables:

- Data-in-hand recommendations in real time
- Automated decision pipelines — faster by design
- Automated model retraining with feedback loops

D. Enhanced User Experience

Future versions of the system could provide more interactive and user-friendly features, such as:

- Dynamic infographics for improving data visualisation.
- Create user-centric reports depending on user
- An AI-based chatbot with some real time support.

E. Security and Privacy Enhancements

- Potential improvements to secure and comply with regulations:
- Differential privacy techniques for secure data by implementing them to sensitive information.
- Improving Access Control through Role-based Authentication
- Regular security audits to find the holes.

VI.CONCLUSION

The given research study deals with the producing enhanced doctor recommendation ,medicine recommendation and precautions generation for a given disease or symptoms using Machine learning. The Model which has been trained using the datasets of the patients from health care platforms across helps in producing efficient results.The inclusion of the

Artificial Intelligence and Model in a healthcare platform and site improves the user friendliness.

The system can reduce the traditional limitations of the patient consultation and medicine prescription where the patient has to personally reach the doctor and receives recommendation for the medicine and suggestive precautionary measures. The large dataset present across the healthcare platforms that includes patient medicinal history, doctor recommendations for a medicine associated with a disease and medicine details present currently give efficient results. The inclusion of the technology in a website platform for doctor consultation would help the platform to suggest the doctors best as per the disease and the locations. The inclusion of the Artificial Intelligence would enhance the results .

The ML model has been modelled using random forest classifiers with the labels such as disease, location, symptoms that would significantly affect choosing the target label doctor . The average accuracy lies in between 70% -90%. The ML is run on a server using the python flask and its functionality could be accessed using the API that has been created for it.

As a summary, improvements in the technological fields such as Machine Learning and Artificial Learning really bring in exponential advancements in the medical and healthcare fields. This literally brings greater health related services to the people (Deepak Kumar).

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